

Social Cognition in Autism:

Predicting Task-Based Neural Activity From Resting State Connectivity

Sahu, A.¹, Shukla, V.², Xie, L.³, Wang, Y.⁴

¹ Department of Psychology, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada.

² Department of Psychiatry, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi, India

³ Brain and Mind Institute, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Shatin, Hong Kong SAR, China

⁴ Sino-French Engineer School, Beihang University, Beijing, China

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Abstract

Understanding Social Cognition (SC) in Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is challenging due to difficulties in obtaining task-evoked fMRI data. This study developed a predictive model using resting-state fMRI (rs-fMRI) to estimate task-related brain activity in ASD. We trained an Activity Flow Mapping (AFM) model on Typically Developing Controls (TDC) individuals from the Human Connectome Project (HCP) and applied it to ASD rs-fMRI data from the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE). While predicted ASD brain activity was not significantly different from social cognition task activations, key social brain regions showed deviations linked to ASD symptoms. Despite limitations, this method demonstrates the potential of using rs-fMRI to predict ASD social task-evoked neural activity, offering a flexible, non-invasive method for future research, diagnosis, and interventions.

Introduction

Social cognition (SC)—the ability to understand and predict others’ thoughts and emotions—relies on a network of regions, including the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC), anterior insula, amygdala, Superior Temporal Sulcus (STS), Temporoparietal Junction (TPJ), and Anterior Cingulate Cortex (ACC) (Blakemore, 2008; Carrington & Bailey, 2009). In Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), disrupted connectivity within this social brain network contributes to hallmark social deficits, such as altered Default Mode Network (DMN) connectivity and atypical posterior STS (pSTS) activity during mental state attribution tasks (Hong et al., 2019; Kassraian-Fard et al., 2016).

Resting-state fMRI (rs-fMRI) has advanced ASD research by identifying atypical Functional Connectivity (FC) patterns, such as under-connectivity in the DMN and over-connectivity in sensory/salience networks, which correlate with social impairments and repetitive behaviours (Hull et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2021). However, task-based fMRI, which directly measures cognitive engagement, faces challenges in ASD due to motion artefacts, sensory sensitivities, and symptom heterogeneity, limiting its applicability (Santana et al., 2022).

Emerging evidence suggests that rs-FC can predict task-based activity, bridging gaps where task data is unavailable. Studies in schizophrenia and neurological disorders demonstrate that rs-FC accurately predicts task-evoked activation (Cole et al., 2014, 2016; Tik et al., 2021; Jia et al., 2020). Machine learning approaches, such as BrainSurfCNN, have successfully applied transfer learning to predict task FC from rs-FC across datasets (Ngo et al., 2022).

Despite findings linking task-based FC to social and cognitive deficits in ASD, few studies integrate rs-FC with task activations. Given that ASD (Autism Spectrum Disorder) and TDC

(Typically Developing Controls) individuals share similar rs-FC patterns (Cherkassky et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2021), predictive modelling offers a non-invasive, scalable approach to estimate task-specific SC deficits. This study explores Activity Flow Mapping (AFM) to predict ASD task activations using rs-FC, leveraging TDC data as a reference to model ASD-specific connectivity.

Methods

Resting-state and task-based fMRI data were obtained from the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) and the Human Connectome Project (HCP) Young Adult S1200 release. All analyses were performed using the Automated Anatomical Labeling (AAL) atlas, focusing on 84 cortical regions.

For ABIDE, .1D resting-state time-series data were interpolated and reduced from 116 to 84 ROIs to match HCP parcellation. FC matrices were computed using Pearson correlation for 408 ASD and 475 neurotypical participants. ADI-R communication scores were cleaned and used in behavioral correlation analysis.

HCP task fMRI data were extracted from a Theory of Mind task and reduced to 84 AAL ROIs. Resting-state data ($84 \times 1200 \times 1096$) and task activations ($84 \times 20 \times 1096$) were processed. FC matrices were computed using both Pearson correlation and multiple regression.

Subject-level FC matrices were computed using both Pearson correlation and multiple regression. Task activations were predicted by modeling each ROI's activation as a weighted sum of all other ROIs, weighted by resting-state FC. Predictions were generated for HCP (within-dataset), and for TDC and ASD participants from ABIDE (cross-dataset). Prediction accuracy was calculated by the Pearson correlation between actual and predicted activations

across ROIs for each subject and task. Prediction error maps were computed by subtracting predicted activations from actual HCP activations.

ROI-wise correlations between predicted activations and ADI-R scores were computed for ASD participants. All visualizations were performed using Nilearn, Matplotlib, and BrainSpace. All analyses were implemented in Python (version 3.11.12).

The full pipeline and notebooks are available at:

https://github.com/Wyw021214/ISP_autism/blob/main/ISP_MindMappers_Final_Micropublication.ipynb

For more detailed methods, please refer to the supplementary information.

Results

The actual task-evoked activations from HCP participants (Figure A1) showed robust engagement of frontal and parietal regions. AFM using HCP resting-state data accurately predicted these activations (Figure A2), demonstrating high correspondence. Predictions generated from ABIDE neurotypical resting-state data (Figure B1) moderately approximated HCP task activations, whereas predictions from ABIDE ASD data (Figure B2) were notably weaker and more spatially diffuse. Difference maps (Figures C1, C2) revealed that prediction errors were more pronounced for the ASD group, particularly in frontal and temporal areas. ROI-wise analyses (Figure D1) showed that reduced predicted activation in specific ROIs was associated with higher ADI-R communication impairment scores, suggesting functional relevance of the predicted patterns. Please refer to the supplementary material for further details.

Model accuracy was assessed using Pearson correlations between ABIDE-predicted FCs and ADI-R Communication subscore, yielding significant correlations ($p < 0.05$). The spin permutation analysis yielded a significant p-value of 0.001, indicating that the observed correlations are unlikely to be due to chance. The regions with the highest positive correlations to ADI-R scores were the right cingulate anterior ($r = 0.191$, $p = 0.00074$) and the right temporal middle ($r = 0.175$, $p = 0.00200$). In contrast, the left postcentral ($r = -0.203$, $p = 0.00033$) and the left frontal inferior orbital ($r = -0.213$, $p = 0.00016$) exhibited the highest negative correlations with ADI-R scores.

D.1: Correlation between predicted ROI activations and verbal score

Figure 1: Visualisation of brain regions

Fig A1. HCP Task activations

Fig A2. HCP task predictions

Fig B1. ABIDE-TDC predictions

Fig B2. ABIDE-ASD predictions

Fig C1. Activation differences ABIDE-TDC and HCP

Fig C2. Activation differences ABIDE-ASD and HCP

Fig D1. Correlation between predicted ABIDE-ASD activations and communication scores

Discussion

The heterogeneity of ASD and differences in dataset demographics likely influenced results (Gonzalez-Gadea et al., 2014; Lenroot & Yeung, 2013).

In our analysis, we identified several key regions with significant correlations to the ADI-R Communication subscore, including the right cingulate anterior ($r = 0.191$, $p = 0.00074$), right postcentral gyrus ($r = 0.175$, $p = 0.00200$), left postcentral gyrus ($r = -0.203$, $p = 0.00033$), and left frontal inferior orbital gyrus ($r = -0.213$, $p = 0.00016$). These regions are implicated in networks that play a critical role in the pathophysiology of ASD. The right cingulate anterior and right temporal middle are part of the Default Mode Network (DMN), which is known to exhibit altered connectivity in ASD, particularly in regions involved in self-referential processing and social cognition (Raichle et al., 2001; Uddin et al., 2013). The left postcentral gyrus, connected to the salience network, is involved in sensory processing. Dysregulation of this network has been associated with difficulties in attention and social behavior in ASD (Seeley et al., 2007; Uddin et al., 2013). The left frontal inferior orbital gyrus, related to executive functions and

social behavior regulation, has been linked to impulse control and social interaction difficulties in ASD (Müller et al., 2009). These findings support existing literature on DMN and salience network dysregulation in ASD, suggesting that alterations in these networks may contribute to the social communication impairments observed in the ADI-R subscore.

Limitations and Future Directions

ABIDE lacks standardized task-based fMRI data tailored to ASD, and suffers from substantial site heterogeneity, noise, and inconsistent acquisition and preprocessing pipelines—factors that undermine the reliability of FC estimates and necessitate reliance on proxy activations like those from HCP, which may not fully capture ASD-specific neural dynamics.

The TD ABIDE predicted activations were conducted to test the robustness and generalisability of the AFM model. Note that the TDC ABIDE predictions did not align with the HCP predictions, suggesting a lack of robustness of the AFM model.

Although AFM allowed us to borrow HCP social-cognition activations as a transfer-learning proxy for ABIDE, AFM depends on task contrasts that are unique to the dataset it was trained on, limiting its effectiveness in generalising or transferring predictions to external datasets like ABIDE. As a simple linear mapping of connectivity weights onto task-evoked activations, AFM lacks the data-driven optimization of machine-learning approaches, making it more useful for visualization than for precise prediction. Incorporating more sophisticated frameworks—such as regularized regression, kernel methods, or deep learning—could capture nonlinear patterns and improve accuracy. Nonetheless, AFM remains a noninvasive, scalable first step; future work should leverage higher-resolution parcellations, ASD-tailored tasks, and advanced predictive models to refine and validate brain-behavior inferences in autism.

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Supplementary material:

Datasets:

Human Connectome Project- Young Adult

We utilised the Human Connectome Project-YoungAdult (HCP-YA) 1200 release (Barch et al., 2013), which was preprocessed using the Automated Anatomical Labeling (AAL) Atlas. The ATLAS initially had 116 ROIs which were reduced to 84 ROIs. We used all subjects' resting state and social cognition (mental) task fMRI data.

We focused on the social cognition task (also referred to as the Theory of Mind task), in which participants watched short (~20-second) video clips depicting geometric shapes (e.g., triangles, squares) interacting in ways that implied intentionality. After each clip, participants were asked to judge whether the interaction was meaningful—i.e., suggestive of mental states—or appeared random. This task was adapted from the original animations designed by Castelli et al. (2002), which have been widely used to probe theory of mind and mentalizing processes.

Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE):

ABIDE provided structural, functional fMRI data, and behavioral data from 539 individuals with ASD and 573 typical controls collected from different sites worldwide. We utilized the functional data from the individuals with ASD through the preprocessed connectome project. We acquired ASD-only preprocessed data using the CPAC pipeline with the `filt_global` strategy and the `roi_aal` derivative, which provides region-of-interest (ROI) time series data based on the AAL atlas (Cameron et al., 2013).

ABIDE Preprocessing and Data Analysis

ABIDE preprocessing involved removing ROIs 85 to 116 to ensure the final dataset contained 84 ROIs, matching the HCP atlas format for consistency.

For the analysis, we averaged the SOCIAL_MENTAL task activations across the two conditions and across all subjects in the HCP dataset. This resulted in a single average activation vector of shape (84,), which was then applied uniformly across all ABIDE subjects to predict their activations using their functional connectivity (FC) matrices.

In terms of predictive methods, two approaches were tested. Both methods attempted to use the HCP task contrasts as a proxy to apply to the ABIDE data. In Method 1, we applied a shared average activation vector across ABIDE subjects. In Method 2, we attempted to learn a linear model on the HCP data by training a ridge regression model for each ROI using the functional connectivity profiles of the other ROIs. However, Method 2 produced poorer prediction accuracy and lower correlation with the actual HCP data compared to Method 1. Consequently, Method 1 was selected and continued for the ASD dataset analysis.

ADI-R Scores

Autism Diagnostic Interview-Revised (ADI-R) scores are standardized, semi-structured caregiver interviews used to assess developmental history and symptom severity in individuals with autism. The ADI-R focuses on three core domains: social interaction, communication and language, and restricted and repetitive behaviors (Lord et al., 1994).

In this study, we extracted ADI-R verbal scores for ABIDE subjects with available phenotypic data and matched them to corresponding predicted regional activations. For each of the 84 brain regions (ROIs), we computed Pearson correlation coefficients between the predicted activations and ADI-R communication scores across subjects. ROIs with p-values below 0.05 were considered statistically significant, and we visualized ROI-wise correlations to identify brain regions where predicted activity was most strongly associated with symptom severity.

Model accuracy was assessed by examining how well the predicted functional connectomes from the social cognition task corresponded to individual differences in phenotypic data (e.g., ADI-R scores), rather than directly comparing predicted and actual activation values. This approach provides an indirect validation of the model's ability to capture relevant brain-behavior relationships.

Predicted ASD ROIs - Correlations with ADI-R Scores and p-values

Frontal Inferior Orbital Left (ROI 55) - $r = -0.213$, $p = 0.00016$

Postcentral Left (ROI 29) - $r = -0.203$, $p = 0.00033$

Cingulate Anterior Right (ROI 24) - $r = 0.191$, $p = 0.00074$

Postcentral Right (ROI 30) - $r = 0.175$, $p = 0.00200$

Heschl's Gyrus Left (ROI 52) - $r = 0.173$, $p = 0.00218$

Frontal Superior Orbital Left (ROI 18) - $r = -0.166$, $p = 0.00339$

Frontal Middle Left (ROI 4) - $r = -0.169$, $p = 0.00278$

Fusiform Right (ROI 73) - $r = 0.167$, $p = 0.00316$

Frontal Inferior Triangular Left (ROI 7) - $r = -0.160$, $p = 0.00475$

Temporal Inferior Left (ROI 70) - $r = 0.154$, $p = 0.00660$

Frontal Superior Right (ROI 80) - $r = 0.152$, $p = 0.00742$

Frontal Superior Orbital Right (ROI 14) - $r = 0.150$, $p = 0.00830$

Frontal Middle Right (ROI 1) - $r = 0.143$, $p = 0.01164$

Detailed Figure Description:

Strong task-related activations appeared in medial frontal, bilateral visual and motor, and orbitofrontal regions in the HCP dataset [Fig. A1]. Predicted task activations in HCP appeared to be qualitatively similar to actual task predictions [Fig. A2]. While both HCP and ABIDE-TDC (Typically Developing Controls) showed similar regional activations, however, the ABIDE activations were more diffuse in lateral regions [Fig. B1]. The ABIDE-ASD activations showed predictions in bilateral temporal regions, medial frontal cortex and right parietal and ventral occipital regions [Fig B2]. The brain activations in bilateral occipital cortex, ventral medial prefrontal cortex and left parietal cortex suggest ABIDE-TDC predictions failed to fully capture task-evoked increases in these regions. While precuneus, posterior cingulate and parts of cerebellum showed stronger activations in ABIDE-TDC as compared to HCP dataset [Fig C1]. In Fig C2, we found the medial prefrontal cortex, right temporal and bilateral parietal cortex, often implicated in social cognition, were underpredicted in ABIDE-ASD in comparison to HCP, while precuneus, temporal poles and cerebellum were overpredicted. ROIs 31, 56 and 26 indicated strongest negative correlations suggesting higher activation leading to better communication scores, while ROIs 24, 19 and 71 indicated positive correlations suggesting higher activations leading to worse communication scores [Fig D1].

GitHub Repository:

https://github.com/Wyw021214/ISP_autism/blob/main/ISP_MindMappers_Final_Micropublication.ipynb